

Language Acquisition

Part 2 of 3

Genetic Typology of Natural Human Language
Hidden Colors Theory

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ABSTRACT

In this second part, we will highlight the relationship between the theory of the evolution of species and linguistics. The preceding will serve as antecedents to develop a Genetic Typology, following the guidelines established by non-orthodox evolutionary theory that makes explicit the "genetic composition" of all languages. To achieve these objectives, we will invoke the Theory of Hidden Colors, by analogy. A tool used in biology to explain, through the study of mutations (in plants and animals), the genetic mechanism that determines the development of an embryo or a new plant. In this part of the work, we propose to demonstrate that the origin of a new language can be explained similarly as today, it is known that a new species emerges. The research carried out suggests that Protolanguages (the precursors of natural human language) are genetic (social) strategies for communicating the reality apprehended, and therefore, it is not relative because it reflects the vision we have of this reality. The Urlingua (the universal language), on the other hand, is relative because it determines how we interpret the world and our reality in it.

Keyword: Natural language, language acquisition, Psycholinguistics, Transcursive Logic.

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Linguistic taxonomy proposes different ways to classify the languages of the world. The best known are typological and genetic classification. The first is based on the grammatical similarities that define a language. While the second, taking as reference the phylogenetic relationships between the languages that derive from a common language, characterizes a specific linguistic family.

The genetic classification is based on the evolution of languages. Understanding by evolution, in linguistics, the changes and diversification suffered by different languages, with the passage of time. This type of classification is distinguished from any other by the criterion with which the similarities that determine a family are approached, the method used to investigate them and the justification of their use, considering it as if it was the paradigm in the research in this field of knowledge. The latter, according to Greenberg, derives from the fact that the term "genetic" is not a mere metaphor, but a biological parallel with the "evolutionary taxonomy" (Greenberg, 2001).

However, the same author points out that despite the similarity between biological and linguistic evolution, in biology nothing is comparable, for example, to the law of regular phonetic change that allows the reconstruction of ancestral languages (Greenberg, 2005).

Due to the previous inconsistencies, as we anticipated in the first part of this work, the symbiotic analysis called Genetic Typology was decided, with the firm purpose of using the already established sociobiological homology in a coherent and fertile way.

In this second part, we will first address, the possible origin of a new language and the linguistic variability it exhibits, taking as a guide the evolutionary biological process of speciation. Secondly, we will outline a probable genetic origin of natural human language, considering its essential social component as a kind of "cellular composition," whose parallel with biology can be evidenced by the Theory of Hidden Colors.

The proposed approach supports the central hypothesis of this research: "In natural human language the subjective (evident) aspects can be approached from the logic of the proper sense of the universal language of the living beings." From this basic assumption and by an alternative theory of evolution, a secondary hypothesis arises: "In the natural human language the different languages are the product of a genetic evolution manifested through an evolutionary variability."

2.0 GENETIC TYPOLOGY OF NATURAL HUMAN LANGUAGE

In the first place, a parallel between speciation (see Appendix A) and the origin of a new language, can be established by using the theory of punctuated equilibrium (Eldredge & Gould, 1972, Dixon, 2001, p.67). This theory addresses the origin and deployment of species in geological time and proposes that the appearance of a new species is the result of a genotypic (hidden) gradualism that promotes abruptly, phenotypic jumps without intermediate elements. This is opposed to the phenotypic gradualism (see Appendix A) with intermediate evolutionary stages (the missing link) proposed by Darwin (1859). Darwin used to support his theory the analogy between linguistic families that came from a common ancestor and species, as well as the historical linguistics of Schleicher (1853) (see Appendix B). This evolutionary alternative is also very similar to what is usually found in different languages, whose changes are not gradual. (Figure 1 - left)

In the second place, we can propose a simile between evolutionary biological novelty and linguistic variability. Two processes explain the evolutionary novelty. One accepted by the majority is the splicing of RNA (Figure 1 - center). In this figure, we can see that the DNA molecule that occupies a gene has a particular disposition.

Fig. 1. Specification and evolutionary novelty

In the genes are the *exons* that contain the information to produce a given protein. Each *exon* encodes a specific portion of the entire protein. In eukaryotic cells, (see Appendix A) the exons are separated by extended regions of DNA called *introns* which have no apparent share in the protein code. The figure shows the different stages through which the complete process of protein-coding must pass. It highlights the presence of a kind of "machine" consisting of a hundred proteins and half a dozen small molecules of RNA, which is responsible for sectioning the introns, discarding them, and cause the "splicing" of the exons to form the mature RNA. This will form a certain protein, and a "folding" process will give it its specific functionality (Sampedro, 2002, p.49).

The other biological mechanism that we will invoke to try to explain the linguistic variability is the mixture of *exons* (Figure 1 - right). The *exon* is a functional unit, not of the gene (see Appendix A), which is like a "text," but of the protein that the gene gives meaning (Doolittle & Gilbert, 1978). Linguistically, the *exon*, as a grammatical particle, would be a "discursive marker." Impromptu unions of *exons* of neighboring genes are assumed in a single gene, thus grafting, novelty and evolutionary variability without altering the usual "reading" of the "text." True discursive markers that, without syntactic participation in the base text, serve to establish relationships between functional modules and, therefore, give rise to a new function, different from those that were encoded in the genomic DNA (or original text). Promotion of an evolutionary novelty that, in the case of natural language (preserving analogies), could entirely explain the emergence of new languages.

It is interesting to know that bacteria have introns in some of their genes and use RNA to get rid of them. The only difference is that in this case, the intron's RNA is the one that makes the cut and the splice. The chemical reactions that are carried out in this process are the same as during the operation of the eukaryotic machine. Therefore, it is possible that this bacterial RNA, when evolving, has been transformed into the small RNA molecules of the "splicing machine" that in eukaryotes ends up being the very center of coordination of all the "machines" that intervene in the complex reading of gene expression. This mechanism is in everything equivalent to the PAU (universal autonomous pattern) that links, as a universal language that we analyzed in the first part of this work, all the real systems (see Appendix A) and gives support to the origin of all languages.

The biological (theoretical) mechanism suggested is useful because it, on the one hand, supports a genetic typology of natural human language. On the other side, it will serve us later, when we try to explain why the different grammatical structures keep a specific order, and therefore, they fulfill a particular function in each language. The latter is essential because it makes vernacular expression something that may or may not share structures and/or meanings with

another, no matter how close it may be (For example: Spanish and Basque). That leads to the typology based on the syntax, used habitually, lose transcendence.

3.0 GENETICS OF NATURAL HUMAN LANGUAGE

Having the elements provided in the previous point, we will try to outline a possible origin of the natural language of man. We start from the assumption that the subjectivity or the "constructor of subjectivity" (Salatino, 2018) is the equivalent of a eukaryotic cell, with its evident (superficial) nucleus and one or more 'organelles' (deep). This would allow distributing the natural language according to the domain (nucleus) and a series of modalities (organelles) that would fulfill a typification function.

The sense that we assign to this taxonomic possibility is based on the fact that, by taking the theory of evolution as a support, according to an alternative view, it is possible to answer as to why there are as many languages as there are and why they are the way they are. In this way, we eliminated in some way the difficulties that the pseudo-evolutionary linguistic approaches of which are not lacking, such as the genetic one, which is determinedly seeking a common origin or an original language, or the one that proposes the influence of the "cultural invasion."

The proposal presented here, although it also seeks a common origin, does not do so from a single origin, but from a universal origin. This is the only way we see of sustaining a "homogenous relational pattern." To the current linguistic-genetic classification, by not getting a common ancestor, it is impossible to explain the pseudo-evolutionary anomalies that are presented step-by-step.

The transcurssive logic that animates our real systems offers the possibility of considering the social as a 'cellular composition' that would sustain, at that level, the culture, as a psychic level to cognition and a biological level to life. In this way, it would be manifested through the sublime expressions of subjectivity: living, knowing and having a symbolic language, thus proving the central hypothesis of this work, displayed in the introduction (Salatino, 2009).

To test the secondary hypothesis about linguistic variability, we will invoke, with due distance, the stages of the genetic program that directs the development, the structuring and the differentiation of the different organs of an embryo, of any species. In this program, there are only two types of genes: those that define the location and those that determine the type of organ. Before different cells begin to specialize, a body scheme is put into operation that indicates the position of the main regions (head, trunk, tail, etc.).

A "homeotic" gene (see Appendix A) is one that indicates, within the development program, the location of the organs along the anteroposterior axis [syntactic axis] of the embryo. E. B. Lewis (1978) showed that the homeotic genes encoded specific functions of the development pattern by assigning the respective segmental identities. The grouping of these genes could also be determined evolutionarily. That is subtle variants of one another allowed it to acquire new functions that would explain the segmental variability that the corporal plan manifests in different species.

In 1984, W. McGinnis discovers the "homeobox" (Hox - or homeotic box) which are homeotic genes that share a common structure of 180 nucleotides (see Appendix A), belong to the same structural family and have, in the evolutionary history, a common ancestor. The proteins that encode these genes have a variable region whose amino acid sequence (see Appendix A) is very different from one species to another, and a region formed by 60 amino acids, called "homeodomain." These last sequences are located in the same order in the chromosomes of very different animal groups, already present in the ancestors of vertebrates and insects, before the Cambrian (Dessain & McGinnis, 1993) [Universals?]. In all animals they fulfill the same mission in embryonic development. That is, the sequences responsible for the development of different parts of the body (legs, eyes, urogenital system, etc.), both in invertebrates and in amphibians, reptiles, birds, and mammals.

Antonio García-Bellido, a Spanish geneticist, was able to demonstrate that the Hox genes specify the development of the different embryonic organs, giving them their "identity." For

example, the Hox genes that determine the development of a mouse eye, introduced in a *Drosophila Melanogaster* (fruit fly), in the different segments that produce its legs, wings, antennae, etc., induce the appearance of "eyes of a fly" in these locations. Therefore, there is a group of genes, which are the same in all species, that define or identify what an "eye" is, and thus with all other organs and body parts of an embryo.

The analysis of the genes carried out by García-Bellido showed the existence of integrated genetic operations, which specify a specific morphology in a combinatorial way. Each process is defined by specific molecular interactions between genes, constituting a "syntagma," considering that genes are like "words." And the words, both in biology and in grammar, are organized in syntagmas (García-Bellido, 1986).

García-Bellido's research showed that Hox genes control the watertight compartments (anterior and posterior) in which the embryo body of the *Drosophila* divides its development. This control is done by few Hox genes in an additive way, modulating many other genes. The "syntagma" of García-Bellido defines the following sequence: a "selector gene" determines what and when to locate the different elements. This information, once adequate for the "regulatory genes" that establish the identity of each element in the anteroposterior and superficial-deep axes, respectively, is transferred to an "encoding gene." Then, it is transmitted to the "realisator genes" that indicate how and where to locate those elements (García-Bellido, 1975).

We will take as a model the genetic discoveries outlined to explain how the control and management of "identities" could arise as structural units of the reality posed by the Transcursive Logic.

An essential consequence of accepting the previous mechanism as a possible regulator of the enormous diversity in all human subjective manifestations, primarily and fundamentally of language, is that such difference then represents only minor adjustments to something that, evolutionarily, was "invented," several million years ago.

The *urilingua* suggested in the first part of this work, in a similar way to *urbilaterian* (see Appendix A) the theoretical ancestor of all modern animals, including man, would already have in the bud the three proposed necessary components of reality, arranged on two levels, one superficial and one deep. As we said, this provision only admits that it is addressed from its syntax, since the only thing that matters here is that everything is in its proper place, just like in the Hox gene, and not the function that each part or element can meet later. For this reason, the six orders that admit the real individual components (S, V, O) (Salatino, 2018) give us, in their chaining, a syntactic way of superficially 'seeing' reality. However, this syntactic disposition is twofold; on the one hand, from the surface it takes a body in the spatial, on the other hand, from the deep, it is imbued in the temporal.

In an attempt to systematize and if we continue to accept the suggested concept of social DNA (Ibidem, p.6) we can then suggest a more detailed organization of this structural complex. In living beings, DNA is packaged mainly in the cell nucleus in their respective chromosomes. The genes that are housed there promote the ordering of a precise sequence of future events that will make the development and growth of that living being. In our proposal, we will also propose a similar structural and, of course, functional integration (Figure 2).

Fig. 2. Suggested genetic composition of "social chromosome"

	DISPOSITION	EXPRESSION
ENCODER GEN → SVO	SUPERFICIAL	DIRECT SUPERFICIAL (evident change)
REGULATOR GEN → OVS	PROFOUND	INDIRECT SUPERFICIAL (no evident change - accumulative)

As the previous figure shows, a so-called "social genome" would be made up of "chromosomes" whose "genes" are divided into two levels: a) a coding level of location and direct

superficial expression, and b) a regulatory level of a deep location, and indirect superficial expression. The latter would be responsible for the "great evolutionary leaps" between the different language families. Variations made possible through cumulative "internal changes" that, after a short time compared to the total evolutionary time, arise (become superficial) as something new and different or evolved, without leaving intermediate traces (genotypic gradualism). This mechanism recalls the evolutionary process suggested by Eldredge and Gould (1972) of the punctuated equilibrium, which we presented previously. This point of view is opposed to the "phenotypic gradualism" lexico-grammatical predominant even today that tries to explain the evolution of languages through 'leafy hierarchical trees.'

The regulatory gene, the equivalent of biological Hox, "does not know" to build verbs, or nouns, or prepositions; only "knows" to temporarily orient each element, whatever it may be, according to the respective grammatical convention and its correspondence or not, with some aspect or a real phenomenon.

The encoder gene to receive the indication of the regulatory gene of what is the position of the verb, for example, provides to the performer genes that 'say' how and where to use the verb.

When in biology, two Hox genes are artificially activated in the same area of the body, the "logic" of the posterior in the row is imposed. To this universal phenomenon, Ginés Morata (Morata & Lawrence, 1975) called it phenotypic suppression. This phenomenon could explain, in our case, linguistic aspects that are appearing in two "contiguous" languages, will end up predominating only in one of them. It is important to note that the phenotypic suppression is telling us that the producer genes are the same for all Hox genes and that the essential difference between a Hox protein and another is the relative affinity for these producing genes. The more posterior a Hox is, the more affinity its protein has for the shared battery of producing genes. These biological phenomena give a possible clue as to why successive duplications of the Hox genes that gave rise to urbilaterian were so easily able to generate a functionally distinct Hox gene family. Almost any small modification, for example, a "letter" of the DNA that exchanged a single amino acid of the duplicated Hox protein would be enough to significantly alter its affinity for the realisor genes.

In our approach, a similar mechanism could help us to explain the differences, sometimes abysmal, that is found between two languages that although very close, geographically or culturally, neither the linguistic classification nor the supposed cultural invasion, can explain their differences.

It is proposed that the changes that were imposed in each duplication that gave rise to the urlingua had as an effect an increase in the affinity (both spatial and temporal) concerning the previous situation. In other words, it depends on the "position" in the row that the degree of affinity grows exponentially, as we will have an opportunity to see. Going in the opposite direction, with decreasing degrees of affinity, would give rise to unfeasible "mutations." Dead languages?

It is evident that the "structures" deployed on the superficial axis have evolved separately in each "linguistic lineage," but the logical foundation of the system must have been the same in all of them: the row of regulatory genes invented by the urlingua. To give a theoretical example: it is possible that the logical foundation of the origin of the verb had arisen from the urlingua and that later, the lexico-grammatical gradualism, would have contributed the sophisticated verbal gliblets that we observed in each existing living language.

In an abstract sense then, superficial structures, which science considers to typify languages, and linguistic particularities, as well as characterizing processes through the verb are similar to urlingua, that is, they handle the same logic, the PAU, thus becoming the most subtle example of non-gradual evolution.

As in this work, in biology, the concept of homology is fundamental (Sampedro, 2002, p.128). For example, the wings are not homologous since both crows and bats have them and yet both have a common ancestor a reptile without wings. Are homologous as appendices, since they share the majority of the genetic system that organizes the cells within each segment. For this reason, they are called segmental polarity genes.

The homology is stable as an abstract operation. In the linguistic field, we propose the existence of these segmental polarity genes that, despite their name, would "know" nothing of syntax, but of abstract designs that are capable of generating pure forms or homeomorphic geometric patterns. Once these genes have raised the outline, other specific genes would give body to that pure form through the contribution of syntactic chords structures. One way to explain the similarities between the different languages, which as you can guess is not superficial, is to accept a universal mechanism equivalent to that described, in all languages.

It is not likely that a language has "invented" a syntactic structure from scratch and as a product of gradual evolution. On the other hand, there could have been an instantiation mechanism (see Appendix A) that allowed to reuse and recombine functional units much more complex than the "orthodox forms." Two concrete examples of this would be, on the one hand, the origin of the subjectivon and on the other, the deciphering of the row of the regulatory gene present in each social chromosome.

Each subjectivon is formed with three complete and previously functional 'genetic elements': S, V, and O. Orthodox gradualism only edits them, hierarchizes them, but it is the polycontexture (see Appendix A), proposed by the Transcursive Logic that generates the noble Heterarchic mechanism (see Appendix A) of interrelations between simultaneous functional instances (Salatino, 2017).

If we imagined for a moment what a system would be like to organize the syntax of a language, we could say that it would be a single regulatory gene (Hox) with a battery attached to the realisor genes. An integrated and previously functional genetic system that would be used by all languages to organize and regenerate their few differentiated structures. The simple serial and divergent duplication of the initial regulatory gene would generate, essentially from within the social genome, a syntactic body organized by more than half a dozen divisions of the original genetic model. Gradualism would thus have the enormous work of polishing and elaborating this system, but not of being its origin, at least in the superficial. It is probable that a mechanism of gradual (continuous) development has been operative in the depth of the "genome", explaining in this way, why only those regulatory genes that could increase their affinity, in successive divisions, with their performing genes would succeed.

Summarizing what has been considered here, we could say that the evolution of languages may not have been gradual. But through models supported in identities that have remained in a state of stable imbalance, product of affinities, and evidenced a particular behavior in situations that may have been internal or external; appreciation of the latter, which, as we have seen, has a solid logical basis.

The row of the regulatory gene (Hox) would be formed by a 'sum', but this sum (logic) is not the one proposed by the hierarchical gradualism (monocontextural - see Appendix A), that is, it is not binary (inclusive), but the generated by a genetic duplication that considered one element at a time but simultaneously. An exclusive logical sum (XOR) that would allow us to deliver a heterarchical structure by enabling each integrating factor to work in a particular context. (see Appendix A)

The duplication of regulatory genes is not distinct because it is serial, but because the original gene already has an integrated network of genes under its control, then the duplication of that gene results in the 'conceptual duplication' of the original model. In other words, the realisor genes do not physically duplicate but go from having a regulator to having six or more, arranged in a single row (Figure 3).

Fig. 3. Genetic aspects of development

Reference: GR: regulator gene

Figure 3 shows the findings in the *Drosophila Melanogaster* and its schematization in a supposed "social chromosome." In this way, we could say that the origin of natural human language is the product of a limited number of instances and its evolution depends on specific mutations that would occur in this mechanism, through time.

Figure 4 proposes one of many ways of coding a row of a regulator gene.

Fig. 4. Theoretical disposition of a row of a regulator gene

References: MSB: most significant bit - LSB: least significant bit

The scheme reveals what is known in computer science as a logical word. A unit of measurement of the amount of information that a programmable electronic device can handle as a semantic entity and which is called a byte (see Appendix A). In turn, the byte is formed by a unitary element: the bit (see Appendix A), arranged in linear succession in groups of eight.

The power of this, in appearance so simple arrangement, lies in that it encloses itself and in so little space, a whole numbering system that allows from storing information or encode orders to comply.

Respecting the original layout, we have highlighted in the figure some elements that in our case, will also be relevant, among them, point out the least significant bit (LSB), and the most significant bit (MSB), as the extreme unit elements in this word 'Pattern'. The degree of significance is given by the exponent (n) that shows the base of the system (2n) (see Appendix A), which grows geometrically from right to left. The degree of significance has great importance in this type of notation because, while allowing us to 'count' (from 0 to ∞), it allows too the calculation of the position in the row of a given element (bit).

On the other hand, and this is very useful for our purpose, if we assign conventionally for example, to each box, the 'control' of a specific syntactic structure, it is enough with the indication of its presence or not in a given language. A particular arrangement of 1s and 0s will provide us with a quick and accurate overview of the syntactic structure of the language in question.

Finally, we have specified in the figure, to approximate the scheme to the biological "Hox row," a division by halves that aims to establish the management of more general structural "locations," mimicking the distribution in compartments of the different segments of the body of a living being.

The structuring of the different levels (superficial and deep) that at first sight may seem disparate and even opposite, actually responds to the same logic. The duplication of the original regulatory gene is not a significant complication, but the attached genes cannot be improvised to give structure to a new level; necessarily in each division, the new regulatory gene 'inherits' the old, at least initially, and thus becomes a 'model of models.' This meta-control is based on at least three fundamental aspects:

- a) Symbiosis,
- b) Duplication of genes that regulate other genes, and
- c) Sequential polarity, which does not serve to define, for example, a certain syntactic structure, but specifies the abstract operation necessary to generate functional geometric patterns of pure forms that can be used for different purposes.

Sequential polarity genes do not need to be contiguous in the "genome" to act in a block. The simple activation of a gene, which can be indicated by a '1' in a row box, can chain all others. The place and time in which a specific gene is activated depending on the zones of the "regulatory DNA," adjacent to the "text" of the gene itself.

These structures are susceptible to mutations (small or large) and a change of this type in the regulatory area of the gene, can act on its own so that this model of segmental polarity genes is reused.

4. HIDDEN COLORS

In all the works produced on Transcurssive Logic, has been used a specific color code. This was not done with an aesthetic sense, but with a practical and methodological one.

The basic contextures (see Appendix A) were assigned respective colors to be able to handle intuitively the logical calculations that arise when operating with them. The choice of colors is not capricious. Instead, it responds in a whole to the physical theory of the colors of light, with its additive and subtractive elements. It follows the RGB code that uses a Cartesian coordinate system in which a space contained in a cube on the side equal to the unit is defined (see Appendix A).

Fig. 5. Binary codes and relations between colors

BLACK	000 is opposite and complementary to 111	WHITE
BLUE	001 is opposite and complementary to 110	YELLOW
GREEN	010 is opposite and complementary to 101	MAGENTA
CYAN	011 is opposite and complementary to 100	RED

Figure 6 establishes the relationship that has been considered between the colors initially assigned, and those that acquire the contextures and the identities that depend on them according to Figure 5.

Fig. 6. Allocation of colors according to color theory

The initial assignment of colors, that is, blue (001) to the subject (S), green (010) to the object (O) and black (000) to ∇ , responds to the fact that the binary (010) each represents the decimal of its valence (see Appendix A), which is 1, 2 and 0, respectively. An apparent exception is the contexture V, which houses the objective or visible change (VO) since with valence 3, it should correspond to the color cyan (011) since it has the corresponding binary. However, it is assigned red (100).

If there is no valence 0, as happens in the universe designed by Peirce, (where only exist the primary, the secondary and the tertiary) we could not find an explanation to the appearances, that is, we could never understand the subjective. This tries to represent in the subjective reality, the red color assigned to the change, with a decimal value of 4 (100 binary), instead of the value 3 that would correspond to its valence. Red is complementary of cyan, we saw it before, and this means that both summed give white, that is, unity. The change referred to by valence 3 is the immanent integration of an apparent change and a hidden change. When in the course of the evolution of subjective reality, both changes are differentiated, the hidden takes the 3 of the valence (cyan or 011), and the superficial or apparent it's complementary. Stay with the 4 or the 100 assigned to the red color, in compliance with the laws that govern the theory of colors and thus respecting, strictly, the basic principles of Transcursive Logic over complex identities. That is, those that are constituted by elements that have the triple relationship of opposition, complementarity, and concurrence, as do the colors of light.

As we can see, are proposing that everything is arranged as if it were "made with colors". Obviously, we are not referring to the colors we perceive as characterizers of what we can scrutinize with our eyes, but to those who, following the same laws that these are not obvious to us, that is, that being hidden serves as a structural metaphor for everything that is contained in the reality we are analyzing. Of these last colors is what we are going to talk about and we are going to do it from a practical case that reflects, with the least possible level of doubt, where is the distinction between two different languages. To reach this demonstration, we will necessarily have to introduce ourselves, in some detail, into the germinal antecedents of the different languages.

4.1 Where are the hidden colors originated?

When we propose, in the first part of this work (Salatino, 2018, p.12), the way in which the process of morphogenesis was carried out in the universal language in the variety of meiotic (sexed) reproduction, we saw the participation of two gametes (50% each) in the generation of a new universal mother tongue (UMT). The equal involvement of the "parents" only is corroborated in the "core" of the new element, where are "stored" the hereditary characteristics, both "paternal" and "maternal."

We can follow the sequence of alternatives that give rise to the hidden colors in Figure 7.

Fig. 7. Hidden colors

Outside the nucleus, that is, in the cytoplasm of the new "descendant," things are not so even. In this sector of the "social cell," the greatest contribution corresponds to REM (or real fact) that acts as "mother." In other words, by joining two compatible and complementary social cells, who represents the "father" contributes, outside of 50% of the nucleus, with one of the "cellular poles": the *black* (first hidden color), that is, gives the 'total absence of colors', so we will characterize it with a '0'. This last contribution certifies the 'sexual union' and thus from a single element, a dimensionless *black point* (0D) is passed to a *line* that extends from the *black* pole (0) to the *white* pole (1) through a continuous grayscale that gives rise to the first dimension (1D = what) of this cellular reality.

From the initial process described, cell development continues on its own and is observed in the evolution that each cell pole shows separately.

The maternal pole unfolds in its basic components: *red*, *green*, and *blue*, since the *white* is the additive synthesis of these three primary sources of color, while the paternal pole remains unchanged. In this way, the second dimension originates from the geometric-functional (2D = when). This means that a *plane* is formed in whose vertexes there are four possible combinations between the two original colors: *black* and *white* (see in the figure). These combinations are: 00 (0) = *black*, 01 (1) = *blue*, 10 (2) = *green* and 11 (3) = *red* (we saw why there is neither the *cyan* nor the *white*). In one of the diagonals of this *plane* that joins the opposite ends (*black* - *red* (which replaces *white*)) is preserved the information in the grayscale.

In a further step towards 'cellular adulthood,' an important evolution of the paternal pole and a minimum of the maternal pole is observed. Thus, the paternal pole, which cannot be differentiated in its components because it has none, is limited to absorbing and reflecting alternatively, the colors emitted by the maternal pole. This process is put into operation by combining, in pairs, the maternal colors reflected so that the color obtained is complementary and opposed to the color absorbed or missing in a particular situation. The previous figure shows a detail of this mechanism and how the appearance of complementary or secondary colors occurs: *yellow*, *cyan*, and *magenta* that show the subtractive behavior of the paternal pole. Since, although the sum of these 'pairs' shows the reflected maternal colors, their difference (algebraic sum) shows us the absorbed colors, which added, give the *black* (000 (0)), as shown in the figure.

As the previous figure is also shown, the third dimension (3D = how) arises from the geometrical-functional when introducing each color in a vertex of a *cube*; a disposition that now, allows assigning to each color the respective complete codes.

The cubic spatial distribution establishes, in the REM, the emergence of two well-detailed levels. On the one hand, the superficial or evident, represented by the primary colors or "emitted" by the maternal pole and that summed to give the *white*. On the other hand, the deep or hidden level

that represents the secondary or complementary colors, or the "absorbed/reflected" by the paternal pole.

In the larger diagonal of this cube, which joins the *black* with the *white*, has been 'saved' the information provided by the 'mother' on the grayscale. That means nothing other than the guide of the sequence of a location of the different colors (primary and secondary) ordered by a continuous and increasing scale of "wavelengths," thus adjusting to the metaphor of the grayscale. Figure 8 summarizes the above.

4.2. What are the relationships between hidden colors and suggested genetics for current languages?

If we adhere entirely to the genetic metaphor to explain the origin of languages, we must think of a set of pre-established instructions that say how a given language should be born and developed. A kind of "user manual," to use an everyday expression.

Fig. 8. Evolution of hidden colors in REM

The ability to interpret this manual is independent of the manual itself, and therefore, it is essential to learn the language in which it is written to follow its guidelines. This language that should be learned is neither more nor less than the universal mother tongue. Learning this language involves the learner and also their environment. This relationship will be responsible for the emergence of the "sense" of what is learned by doing so that their "interpreter" becomes independent of the instructions, that is, of the language itself.

Another derivative of accepting the genetic metaphor is to admit the existence of fertilization, whose direct consequence is the social, genetic exchange between the participants.

Having made it clear that our real systems are linked by the same fundamental logical element (PAU), naturally allows us to state that they are, themselves, structured by a single universal mechanism: the genetic one.

The genetic constitution of the sociocultural system is sustained, as we saw, in the social DNA, and the way between this DNA and a specific "adult" language is transformed in this way, into a question of interpretation.

To clarify the previous statement, we will assume the existence of a biological cell that has the ability to 'translate' messages from its genetic language to our mother tongue. Let us also suppose that on the outer side of its cellular membrane, accessible to us through a microscope, there

is an area that functions as if it were a computer monitor, that is, that it has the possibility of coding a message through the lighting or turn off several luminous spots. This means of communication has the only limitation of being able to work only with two colors: black and white. The message that the cell will make evident on this screen will look very much like a text written in black ink on white paper. The message you will send us will be I'M ALIVE. The above is everything concerning the interface between the cell and us.

Inside the cell, things are very different. There are possibilities to handle all the colors of the spectrum except white and black. Following the suppositions let's say that to be able to arm a message in English, the cell has to be organized in some way. This organization responds to a color scheme, the only material available for these purposes. There is at its core a grid of limited size, which shows a profusion of small squares of different colors distributed, apparently, in a random way. Particular cellular elements are responsible for following an "instruction manual" that tells each one what to do to communicate with other cellular elements, but that is outside the nucleus. To be more precise, they are on the outer surface of the cell membrane, on the supposed screen, and "communicate" that they "dress" in black or white, depending on the occasion. The aforementioned "instruction manual" has only two sheets. Sheet No. 1 has instructions for writing the first two word (s) in English I'M. While the sheet No. 2, to write the third word ALIVE, so that, once read and strictly followed the instructions, you can read, on the external screen, the message that will be displayed in two parts.

Each "instruction manual" has its cover of a particular color. This color tells its bearer, in what small square color of the grid, should be placed. Before a general order, all the cellular elements already located in their respective small squares have to read the first page of their manual, and there they will find only a white or black square and consequently it will be what they will have to communicate to the surface element to show us. Thus, it appears before our amazed eyes, the word I'M.

A new general order, intracellular, says: read the second page and again, only there is a white or black square that will be communicated to the surface as appropriate. The word ALIVE now appears on the screen. It is very easy for any of us to mentally compose the complete message and understand what we were meant to say even though we know absolutely nothing of the existence of the color pattern that served as a guide to issue such a particular message.

Our lack of knowledge about this pattern is based on the fact that we cannot see it. Inside the cell, on the other hand, the opposite happens, none of the elements that intervened to produce this amazing fact, "knows" what I help to build and much less knows the message in question.

As a conclusion then we can say that, knowing something of the intimacy of this particular cell, the pattern of hidden colors served as a frame of reference to make a particular aspect evident.

In the real biological cell, the apparent aspects are promoted by the genes. These genes are evident in their action, as long as they are active and their activity or not ultimately depends on a pattern of hidden colors that act as "keys" for a certain "lock," "open" or "they close" the activity of a given gene. A true binary mechanism, as demonstrated by García-Bellido (García-Bellido et al., 1979, p.101). The metaphor of colors is very appropriate in biological genetics because it allows us to understand that a gradual pattern of activations, a "scale of grays" for example, arrange the correct place in which a specific part of the body should be developed in an adult organism that started from a simple cell formed by the conjunction of two gametes.

In the different languages, following the initial proposal meticulously, we can say that the structuring of the expressions in each of them obeys a hidden color pattern that makes it possible to arrange each expressive element in its correct place. This, without having a relationship with whoever interprets this expression, constitutes the "language in which that language is written," a faithful reflection of its universal mother tongue and that has nothing to do with the language it communicates on the surface. In this way, it is established that the universal mother tongue is something different from the natural mother tongue.

4.3. Basic principles of the functioning of hidden colors

One way to understand the genetic functioning of biology is to analyze mutations. Since a mutation, in general, is the product of inactivation of one or more genes, the superficial expression of this 'anomaly' can guide where it originated and explained the transformations that become evident.

A simple way of understanding what we mean by the term mutation is to imagine what would happen if, in the cell of the previous point, there was an error of interpretation. Half of the cellular nuclear elements, correctly located each in its respective small square of color, read sheet No. 2 of its instruction manual, instead of No. 1 like the rest, to generate the first part of the message. The result, on the surface, would be a message that, at least for us, would be incomprehensible since something like this would appear on the screen: I'MIVE.

Similarly, we propose, in the study of languages, the analysis of the variations that exist between them, but addressing them from the genetic point of view, as we understand the term in this study.

The inactivation of a gene in biology means that either an organ or a group of them will not develop or that a specific function, in a developed organ, will not be carried out.

Before arriving at the comparative analysis between two languages taken as an example, we will do a theoretical exercise to highlight the method to be used in this comparison.

Let's assume that S, V, and O, the superficial components of REM are mutant elements that derive from hidden colors. The white and that ∇ , the black, is the one that fuses the deep components that are a direct consequence of the combination, of the pairs, of the superficial elements and of course, of the deep colors that derive from it. Figure 9 details the proposed scheme.

Fig. 9. Pattern of hidden colors of REM

The chromatic formula of an evolved REM, as deduced from the previous figure, would be S, sv, V, vo, O, os (blue, magenta, red, yellow, green, cyan). The blue and green colors of the surface, in appearance, are opposite and complementary, this means that, for example, if S were lost it would be replaced by O and vice versa.

We propose that in all languages something similar happens to what was stated above and that such alternatives have their roots in the identity of the different elements.

This way of approaching the study will allow us to predict what kind of structure we will have in a language when a distinctive 'regional' characteristic represented by a specific color is "lost" or "is not expressed" in an apparent way. The different surface elements (S, V, O) of a REM are responsible for "producing the hidden colors" and, therefore, also granting different identities, as we have already seen.

Using a scheme as the one proposed, we can suggest that two languages, however different they may seem, may have a similar "hidden disposition." This means that the change that takes place in the appearance is due to only two circumstances: on the one hand, an alteration, not of the code, but of its interpretation and on the other, to an alteration of the element that grants a certain identity. The change occurs due to a variation in the production of hidden colors. In any of the above cases, the hidden colors represent a frame of reference and not a "set of instructions" of how to "manufacture" a verb, a noun or an adjective or any part of a habitual linguistic expression.

The languages we will use in the exercise will be: Spanish and Hopi. The method we will use to establish differences and similarities will then be based on two fundamental premises: 1) Each element of the REM that gives rise to the universal mother tongue from which the considered languages derive, is necessary for a particular hidden color and the combination of these colors will determine a specific segmental identity in a given expression. 2) The habitual role of these constituent elements will be to generate the hidden colors in their respective expressive segments. A variation that "inactivates or removes" one or more of these identity elements will result in the "loss or modification" of color and, therefore, in the modification of any of the identities.

When at a previous point we spoke of a "row of regulatory genes," we were referring precisely to this scheme that we have just raised through the hidden colors and their producing elements.

As the whole mechanism has a binary basis, let's not forget that it operates in the monocontexture of our evident world, the expression of an individual gene can merely be made manifest by means of a '1' placed in the respective "box", as well as its inactivation, by a '0' in that same place.

The above considerations will help us establish a pattern of expressive activity by "tracing" genes that are activated in a given time or that are not activated and remain hidden. The problem then is restricted to how do we distinguish, for example, a specific syntactic structure?

In biology, it is used, to identify if a gene is active or not, the so-called molecular probes (see Appendix A). In our case, we are going to use, metaphorically, a similar procedure. These "probes", which we could call here "syntactic", since the purpose is to find out the correspondence or not between the structures of two expressions, will be of two types: i) those that can recognize a subjectivon, that is, the scale of gray that regulates the structural disposition and ii) those that can recognize a complete expression. The probes of the first type make their recognition in the products that emerged in the transcription stage of a language, that is: very little from its origin, and that has to do with the syntax. While those of the second group, allow tracing elements that appeared in the translation stage, which represents the stage before the definitive linguistic functionalization that appears in the 'mature' language and which gives it semantic handling.

Whorf (1978, p.51) teaches us that, referred to verbs, the Hopi formalizes in different ways the contrast between point and extension in the location of a phenomenon, making it independent of time, space or both. Hopi verbs also have three verb tenses as in Spanish, but grouped in another way:

- 1) Positive (present - past)
- 2) Future
- 3) Generalized (usitative).

The verbs belong to several different conjugations but in the most important of them, in magnitude, is the segmental aspect. That consists of a final reduplication of the CVCV root (consonant, vowel, consonant, vowel), which is in the third person of the singular of the intransitive voice, plus the durative suffix *-ta*, which produces a modification in the meaning of the simple word.

The change would manifest itself through a phenomenon that, indicated by the root and shown in its precise aspect in the form of a manifestation on a point, becomes the externalization of a series of repeated and interconnected segments of a greater phenomenon and a wider segmental

character. Its extension is made in a dimension that remains indifferent to space, time, or both simultaneously.

We will take as the only example the one shown in Figure 10.

Fig. 10. Characterization of the Hopi verb

(Example is taken from Whorf, 1978, p.52)

As the previous figure shows, the generic form (chromatic formula) of the Hopi action would be the punctual and its extension as duration. That is, from our functional geometry would be an event that manifests itself successively as a point (the precise and dimensionless), a line (reduplication, the one-dimensional) and a plane (the extension, the two-dimensional). In this way, the "what" and the "when" are affirmed simultaneously without granting any preponderance to any of them. (Kakectaca, 1978, p.68)

Although given its fundamental characteristics that are:

- I. Not require an external agent.
- II. Manifest recursively After an inapparent change that accumulates; it is triggered by a specific internal situation.
- III. Not have an external duration but internal.

IV. Show activity and result at the same time without specifying where it comes from. ... in fact, it can be assimilated to the dynamics of our ∇ . The above is possible since it is equivalent to a reorganization process, that is, to a non-apparent change that is chromatically summarized in the BLACK and that, as we saw above, is derived from the secondary colors reflected from the surface: MAGENTA, YELLOW, and CIANO.

The Hopi belongs to the domain SOV (Ethnologue, 2018) and according to the transcurssive logic, to the levorotatory variant, contrary to the Spanish that integrates the SVO domain and therefore it is a dextrorotatory language. Figure 11 shows the chromatic formula of both languages.

Fig. 11. Chromatic formulas of Hopi and Spanish

Applying the method of the syntactic probe, in this case, we will see what a Hopi verb becomes when we pass it to Spanish. (Figure 12)

Fig. 12. Genetic variation of a Hopi verb

References: $\circ$: Nucleus - $\bullet$: Gamete - $\curvearrowright$ and $\curvearrowleft$: Direction of rotation - $\oplus$: XOR

As shown in Figure 12, if we paired (an XOR is applied) to the core (SOV) or superficial (*white*) of the Hopi expression, with a "probe" that searches for the superficial of the Spanish, that in this case is the "gamete" of the Spanish expression (O▽S) (from the same levorotatory variant as the Hopi nucleus). We obtain an intermediate product that is neutral. That is, with no direction of rotation whatsoever and which we have identified as a signic splicing, since by mimicking one of the evolutionary stages of natural language (see Appendix A). It tells us, on the one hand, of the common basic logic that have these two languages and, on the other hand, gives meaning to the use in Hopi, of the positive verb tense (present - past).

If the signic splicing obtained we paired (we apply an XOR) with the Hopi gamete (OS▽), the representative of the black in this language, which is clockwise, we get the *white* or superficial of Spanish, which is what we were looking. In this way, we have proven that the syntactic probe was useful because it managed to extract from the Hopi structure its complementary: SVO. It has been demonstrated then, that the expression Hopi that by different sociocultural circumstances had an "inactive gene" in its structure was present when activated, also by the same conditions, in an expression in Spanish. But the concrete and transcendent are that the gene was always present from the very origin in both languages, which, as suggested by what we have just seen, is a common origin.

This analysis, in appearance, is very limited because we have done with a single verb, nevertheless serves to strengthen several aspects of our approach.

First, we demonstrate the operation of the method used. Secondly, look from another perspective of the relationships that link different languages and try some explanation of their differences. Third, by deepening in some way, in the vision of the reality that the Hopi people have, to realize that the real systems (those that structure the subjective reality) are the same for everyone, regardless of geographical or temporal distribution. This confirms the non-provenance of Whorfian relativism since languages seem to be organized according to experience and not vice-versa. The fact that the Hopi language does not contain any reference, neither explicit nor implicit, to the time (Whorf, 1978, p.58), as we understand it and express it poorly in our language, does not mean that this language cannot entirely explain every observable phenomenon in the universe. The latter depends on a question of interpretation and not on a deficient or primitive code as Whorf claims to have discovered.

I disagree with Whorf (Op. Cit.) when he says that time in the Hopi 'disappears.' This contradicts the more than two dozen lexemes that refer to time, which appear in his Hopi-English working Dictionary (unpublished manuscript). (Malotki, 1983, p. 15) I think that it is interpreted differently, and I do not mean that we do it mathematically from the hand of Einsteinian relativity, and they do it from a simple linguistic expression, but that a unique deep chromatic pattern of another way despite having a common origin. We firmly support that in our case, the social inheritance that we will develop in the third part of this work was in charge of modifying the conception of time and making it a slave of the Judeo-Christian heritage. One that consolidated the tripartite linear time that characterizes the Indo-European languages, in spite of deriving from the Latin and the Greek, that had more than three ways to deal with time.

Finally, the simple example presented serves to realize that the reign of the subject-predicate structure that has been and continues to be considered essential to 'think' and 'communicate,' loses sustenance when we learn to "look at it from within." That is, from the polycontexture. Proving that the grammar with a functional center in preaching does not correspond to a conventional universal language but rather, to the subject - action - object scheme (SVO) that we have proposed from the universal language.

It must be considered that the aforementioned scheme only appears to be universal in the languages that derive from Greek. In this language, there are independent things, substances that are denominated with nouns that show properties or attributes, which are designated with adjectives. There are also changes or events in the world that relate such things and are reflected in the verbs. This gives support to the 'doctrine of the kinds of words' in a particular ontology of being. This, which a priori seems to provide an advantage by proposing a suitably uniform structure, gives all these languages a marked ambiguity, as we can see in the following expression: "*Puedo ver la llegada desde el cerro*" (I can see the arrival from the hill).

Here, the term "*llegada*" (arrival) represents a noun (the signal that indicates the end of the competition); an adjective (the goal of a competition); or a verb (the action and result of the arrival of the competitors)?

In the Hopi, not "contaminated" by Western culture, one can "see" inside the polycontexture. Something evident in the analysis the speaker makes of reality regarding "events" instead of things, substances or materials, justifying in this way that a noun in Spanish "*fleco*" (fringe) is a verb "*flecar*" (Aguilar Criado, 1999, p. 115) (make fringes) in Hopi.

Perhaps we can find a more grammatical explanation to what we have presented as an example if we consider that these Hopi verbs, as we said, arise from a root that is in an intransitive voice. The intransitive verbs (Nebrija's neutrals or absolutes) are those that express a complete preaching, that is, they express an idea without the action falling on any person or thing. Given this characteristic, they exclude, de facto, the direct complement since there is no thing independent of the subject that participates in the expression. Among these intransitive verbs are state verbs that serve to express a more or less fixed and stable situation of the subject and whose prototype in Spanish is the verb "*estar*" (to be) (although there are many others, such as: "*llegar*" (to arrive)). In these verbs, the intervention of the subject is more than restricted since it is not the speaker who produces the action, but instead, it is that which manifests itself in him. Grammatically speaking, these verbs occupy an intermediate place between active and passive verbs.

Is not this the border, the Rubicon, that Greco-dependent language crossed, pouncing on ambiguity? *Alea iacta est!* In other words, should the word "*llegada*" (arrival), in Spanish, not having to have been a verb and nothing else? It is thus demonstrated, on the one hand, the ambiguity of the code or everyday language, and on the other, the operative logic of a mechanism of acquisition of natural human language.

5. CONCLUSION

We will recount of the heretofore considered through a couple of definitions:

1) The Protolanguages, that is to say, those that encompass globally the natural human language, are genetic (social) strategies to communicate the reality apprehended and insofar as they are not relative since they do not determine the vision one has of that reality, on the contrary, they reflect it. The *urlingua* (the universal language), on the other hand, is relative to determine how we interpret the world and our reality in it.

2) The selector gene is the strategy used by how many languages have evolved on the planet, an evolution that, although it seems overwhelming, only responds to a few innovative principles. This selector gene should comply with the following properties:

- a. Activate just in one area of the expression (occupy a bit).
- b. Define always the identity of the zone that is active, determining the weight of the byte, that is, the square occupied by a '1'.

c. Do not 'know' about verbs, adjectives or nouns, limit yourself to selecting one structure or another from a repertoire of available forms in each domain, which is different from another. The "decision" of each gene is binary (García-Bellido et al., 1979) and acts in a combinatorial way. In a nutshell, they integrate a byte. The selection function is combined through the "sum" of the powers of 2 (2^n) active, which have a '1' in their box and for this reason (their franc binarism) can be explained from the monocontexture, which is strictly binary.

d. Always act by regulating complex and coherent networks of other genes (realisator genes). A direct consequence of this fact is that the unit of action (operative) of the selector gene is the "social cell" or REM. When a selector gene is inactivated in a certain "social cell" and activated in a different one, in that single cell, a determined element is as if it were in another part of the structure.

e. Although the scope of operation of the selector gene is REM, they give it a series of secondary properties that make coherence significantly affect its interrelation with other REMs. For this reason, the REMs that have the same combination of selector genes active tend to remain together, languages of a particular family, for example, and tend to 'reject' other REMs that exhibit different combinations.

The progressive activation throughout the development, which could happen, for example, in the child, is dividing and subdividing the primitive expression in specific areas, according to the combinatorial code of the selector genes. The latter is a principle that we propose as universal in the development of natural human language, considering it an essential mechanism in its acquisition. Each selector gene and its network of producing genes constitute a "model" that allows evolutionary novelty. The activation of a selector gene in an unusual site until then or in a duplication where a slight mutation occurs will cause the preexisting model to be used in different times and places, generating true morphological and functional novelties brusquely and efficiently. It is in this way that we propose that human languages evolve.

There is a selector gene that gives each segment the property of posterior, as opposed to the previous one. This constitutes an index that determines which is the most significant bit and which is the least significant bit (or which is the first and the last in the sequence) and that also shows how to "read" the sequence. If, for example, we deactivate the selector gene that points to the posterior compartment of the segment, the previous compartment will be duplicated and vice versa, disappearing, in each case, the inactivated compartment. In this way, the reading sequence is broken. That is, instead of being $2^0 \rightarrow 2^7$, it becomes $2^0 \rightarrow 2^3$ or $2^4 \rightarrow 2^7$ twice, respectively. This geometrical-functional disposition is transcendental because that is how we propose that the indications of the four dimensions that we have given to the subjective reality posed in this study are "managed" from the different languages: **S** (what), **O** (how), **V** (when) and **∇** (why). The appearance of a "skeleton" of linguistic expressions in the Urlingua has few possibilities, and one of them is instantiation (as we saw).

The generation of 'models' from other models 'molds,' arises from the progressive increase in the powers of $2^0 \rightarrow 2^7$, which are represented in the dimensional possibilities of a byte. There is a byte that when governing these dimensions says how many models to use and at the same time, when and where to use them. The proposed ancestor of all languages (urlingua) is likely to have been built by genetic models, and its subsequent evolution has mostly been based on instantiating, reusing and then recombining these practically intact models.

Evolution is the archetype of the subjective and above all of the human subjectivity. On the one hand, because our brain is the result of this evolution, but on the other side and even more critical, because the subjective aspects that characterize the man beyond his life (knowledge and symbolic language) are the exclusive product of the emerging psycho-bio-sociocultural, all aspects, purely subjective.

From the evolutionary achievements of man, we can say everything and without fear of making mistakes, mentioning only one of them: the symbolic language, since this implies, in the first place being alive and therefore, grasping, understanding, elaborating (thinking) and

communicating. The symbolic natural language is our indelible evolutionary mark, and the *urlingua* is a proposal for a complex and universal biological solution, which occurred only once in the history of the earth, which would explain why this evolution has left no evidence of a gradual transition.

In the third and last part of this paper series, we will analyze the general aspects of the acquisition of natural language and the relevance of linguistic universals, lexical contextures, and sociocultural heritage.

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APPENDIX A

DNA and RNA: are the nucleic acids that form the basis of our genome or set of chromosomes of a cell. (Author's Note)

Amino acid: an organic acid that forms the basis of proteins. (Author's Note)

The base of the system: the base of the binary system is 2, as well as that of the decimal system, is 10.

Bit: denomination that derives from the apocoptation of the English expression: binary information digit. (Author's Note)

Byte: the term coined in 1957 by W. Buchholz to indicate a continuous sequence of 8 bits.

The eukaryotic cell: is the cell that has a cytoplasm surrounded by a membrane (cell membrane) and also, unlike prokaryotic cells, has an organized cell nucleus where the hereditary material including DNA, which is the base of the cell, is housed heritage.

Speciation: It is known as speciation or cladogenesis to the process by which a population, reproductively isolated from its mother species, gives rise to another or other species. (Author's Note)

Evolutionary stages of natural language: the following table shows the three stages through which our natural language passed through evolutionary history (Salatino, 2009). In each stage, it can be seen from its "genetic composition" to its degree of integration.

	VVV INSTINCTIVE COMMUNICATION	OVO EMOTIONAL COMMUNICATION	SVO EMOTIVE COMMUNICATION
ACTIVITY	Instinctive FAP innate trends primitive, specific and non-planned.	Mixed FAP modifiable Externalization unconscious and not elaborate, that can be modified with the experience.	Learned FAP acquired Not always represent internal states. Conform to norms. They are conscious and elaborated.
FOCUS AND SUBSTRATE	SUBJECT simple animals and plants	INDIVIDUAL (social subject) Animals	GROUP (person) Man
SPACE-TEMPORAL FRAME	BIOLOGICAL Present	PSYCHO-BIOLOGICAL Past-Present	PSYCHO-BIO-SOCIO- CULTURAL Past-Present-Future
FUNCTION AND OBJECTIVE	STRATEGIC LIFE	STRATEGIC ENVIRONMENT	STRATEGIC SOCIETY
LANGUAGE	TAXIC	SIGNIC	SYMBOLIC

 DEGREE OF EVOLUTIONARY INTEGRATION

References: FAP (Fixed Action Pattern) - S: subject - O: object - V: action

Exon: a segment of a gene and its corresponding transcript that remains in a mature messenger RNA, after the elimination of the introns. (Author's Note)

Phenotype: a set of visible characters that shows an individual as a result of the interaction of its genotype and its immediate environment. (Author's Note)

Gen: is the ordered sequence of nucleotides in the DNA molecule that contains the information to make other larger molecules that fulfill specific organic functions; e.g., proteins. (Author's Note)

Genotype: a set of genes that resides in the nucleus of all the cells of a living being. There the genetic information is lodged in the form of DNA that determines the phenotype of an individual.

Heterarchy: a term introduced by McCulloch in 1945 to refer to the situation of interdependence that must exist between different levels or subsystems in which different processes are developed simultaneously. It is considered, as a relational structure, complementary to the hierarchy.

Homeosis: a concept developed by the English biologist and geneticist William Bateson (1861-1926). Through it he defined the acquisition by an organ of the characteristics of another organ:

... the essential phenomenon is not that there has been a change, but that something has been changed into the likeness of something else. (Bateson, 1894, p.85)

Bateson described in this way, the defective patterns in segmented animals, in which the structure of a segment was replaced by a different structure, typical of another segment. The principle elaborated by Bateson has the merit of suggesting the presence of natural serial repetitions and an organization of the complex based on discontinuous units.

Instance: Computer term derived from a concrete manifestation of an abstraction that turns out to be a model of concrete or prototypical things of the real world. (Author's Note)

Monocontexture: it is called contexture (Günther, 1979) to a domain in which there are only two logical values (binary logical domain), and the postulates of classical logic are respected. The monocontexture can be seen as a universe where reality is strictly hierarchical, that is, where causality is linear (cause, then effect). In it there is only place for an ontological niche (continent), be it that of an object, of a subject or of the transformation that binds them, and their respective contents. (Salatino, 2009)

Nucleotide: is the organic molecule formed by a nitrogenous base (adenine, guanine, thymine, cytosine or uracil), a sugar (ribose (RNA) or deoxyribose (DNA)), and one to three molecules of phosphoric acid (AMP, ADP, and ATP) is the elementary component of nucleic acids: DNA and RNA (Author's Note)

Generic universal autonomous pattern: (PAU) fundamental logical core of subjective reality. An ontological-relational pattern that shows a complex structure, that is, its structural elements have a triple relationship of opposition, complementarity, and concurrency (simultaneity).

Policontexture: the domain where multiple contextures interrelate. Relationships are between continents, not between contents. Thus, the context or ontological niche of the object is related to the contexture of the subject, and this relationship defines the subjectivity that is lodged in a different contexture. Transcursive logic determines four interrelated essential contextures. The contexture of the subject (S), the contexture of the object (O), the contexture of the transformation (V) that links them, apparently, in a direct way, and the contexture of the non-evident transformation (∇) that indirectly relates them. In this last contexture lies subjectivity.

Protein: chemical substance formed by amino acids (essential organic acids), and fundamental material of plant and animal cells. (Author's Note)

Real systems: aspects in which the subjective reality has been arbitrarily divided with the object of its study. There are three: psycho-internal, bio-external and sociocultural.

RGB system: each primary color is arranged in one of the three Cartesian axes of a cube, and each assumes an arbitrary value between 0 and 255. The figure shows a "diffuse cube" with all possible

combinations between the colors primary. The color of the sample arises from the "weight" of each color.

Molecular probes: they are molecules of different degree of complexity (RNA or proteins) that, being complementary to the molecules that are searched or tracked, adhere to them if they exist in the organism in which they are sought. Using a biochemical contraption, the complex: molecule sought + molecular probe, stains with a specific color, so it is easy to locate in the ocular observation, the place or places where that gene studied is expressed. (Guillén et al., 1995)

Urbilateria: first bilateral animal in the evolutionary history.

Valence: in Transcursive Logic represents the "relational force" between the basic textures. (figure): S (subject) - O (object) - V (apparent transformation, evident or quantitative change) - ∇ (non-apparent transformation, hidden or qualitative change)

References: $\rightarrow$, $\Rightarrow$, $\Rightarrow$: valences

APPENDIX B

Darwin's theory and linguistics

August Schleicher, in 1853, published his "genealogical tree theory," to establish the kinship between a mother tongue and the Indo-European languages known inspired by the *Systema Naturae* of Linnaeus. (Figure A1)

Fig. A1. Representation of the Schleicher Stammbaumtheorie

(Excerpted from Schleicher, 1853, page 787)

But the concrete thing is that Schleicher strongly adheres to the idea of evolutionism, after reading the publication of Darwin, in 1860, as he leaves it recorded in a letter sent to Ernst Haeckel (1863), the great defender of Darwinism in Germany. In *Die Deutsche Sprache* (1860) on page 28, we can see an arborescent scheme that tries to explain the origin of the different linguistic families from an original language (Ursprache) (Figure A3). Scheme very similar to that published by Darwin in 1859 (Figure A2), and according to the correlation that establishes in Chapter XIII, between languages and biological species:

“It may be worthwhile to illustrate this view of classification, by taking the case of languages. If we possessed a perfect pedigree of mankind, a genealogical arrangement of the races of man would afford the best classification of the various languages now spoken throughout the world; and if all extinct Languages, and all intermediate and slowly changing dialects, had to be included, such an arrangement would, I think, be the only possible one. Yet it might be that some very ancient language had altered little, and had given rise to few new languages, whilst others (owing to the spreading and subsequent isolation and states of civilization of the several races, descended from a common race) had altered much, and had given rise to many new Languages and dialects. The various degrees of difference in the languages from the same stock, would have to be expressed by groups subordinate to groups; but the proper or even only possible arrangement would still be genealogical; and this would be strictly natural, as it would connect together all Languages, extinct and modern, by the closest affinities, and would give the filiation and origin of each tongue.” (Darwin, 1859, p. 422)

Fig. A2. Arborescent structure of Darwin

(Excerpted from Darwin, 1859, p.128)

Figure A3. A common ancestor

(Excerpted from Die Deutsche Sprache, 1860, p.28)

We can also see schemes like the previous one, in other works by Schleicher. For example, in Darwinism Tested by the Science of Language (1863, p.70). (Figure A4)

